

SURVIVAL STRATEGIES OF NON-WORKING INDIVIDUALS IN DAVAO REGION**Abellanos, Gaudencio G^{*1}**

ORCID Number: 0000-0003-1648-5797

Fernandez, Simeon C²

ORCID Number: 0000-0001-7939-1718

Jayagan, Regina Grace B³

ORCID Number: 0000-0002-5863-5493

Labastin, Jonah Lou R⁴

ORCID Number: 0000-0002-2704-5933

Lulab, Lindy C⁵

ORCID Number: 0000-0001-8339-6220

Sajid, Javier⁶

ORCID Number: 0000-0003-0652-1758

javiersajid@gmail.comgaudencioabel@gmail.comChum_sfc@yahoo.comlindyclulab@yahoo.comRgbjayagandole11@gmail.comlabastinjl@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

This study aimed to identify the determinants of survival strategies of non-working individuals as well as the development of a framework utilizing an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) technique. The study was conducted in Davao Region with 110 non-working individuals from different areas in the region as sample respondents. A questionnaire was the research instrument in the gathering of data and was presented to an examiner for content validity. Rotated component matrix discarded 17 items out of 30 and categorized the 13 remaining items into five dimensions. The determinants of survival strategies of non-working individuals revealed five different factors which include strengthen interpersonal attachment, availment of outreach programs, involvement on community celebration, supplication from public and adaptive to harsh or unpleasant environment. A framework of survival strategy was developed.

Keywords

Survival strategies, non-working individuals, exploratory factor analysis, interpersonal attachments, outreach programs, community celebration, public, unpleasant environment, Davao City, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

People in every society, may it be rural or urban, have diverse necessities with different strategies to satisfy their needs. The socio-economic status of individuals defines the needs to be achieved in order for them to survive.

This study is anchored on Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs which states that people are motivated to achieve certain level of needs and that these needs precede over others. The most basic need is for physical survival, this is the first thing that motivates human behavior. Once this level is fulfilled, people tend to achieve higher levels. (McLeod, 2017)

This study will gather insights and draw out a conceptual framework on different strategies for survival that non-working individuals practice in their everyday lives.

FRAMEWORK

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs states that people are motivated to achieve certain level of needs and that these needs precede over others. The most basic need is for physical survival, this is the first thing that motivates human behavior. Once this level is fulfilled, people tend to achieve higher levels. (McLeod, 2017)

Figure 1: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

According to Cordero-Scales, et.al. (2016), "In the event of unemployment, everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security".

To cope with daily hardships, poor people gain strength from family and social activities. They also rely on each other through socialization and debt of gratitude from others. (Rosales, Antonio 2015)

Merriam-Webster (2018), defines non-working individual are not considered part of the labor force and therefore they are not considered unemployed.

Strengthen Interpersonal Attachments. Consistent belongingness (Baumister,R.F, 1995) appears to have multiple and strong effects on emotional pattern and cognitive process According to (Bolby, 1992) sense of belongingness to a greater human whole that has provide essential glue which holds together individuals dedicated same goals and starting same goals. (Smith et.al. 1999) argued that although person to group bonds differ from close interpersonal relationship, in so many ways, the human need to remain emotionally close to depend on social groups implicate the same subsystem and functions that regulate person-to-person attachment.

Availment of Outreach Program. Sufficient clothing or the right of clothing (Wikipedia.org) is recognized as a human right in various international human rights instruments.

Involvement on Community Celebrations. Food security is formidable development challenges of Ethiopia although the country was witnessed promising changes in economic growth (FAO et.al., 2015) in addition food security is a situation that exist when all people, at all times have physical and economic access to sufficient safe and nutritious. However, social structures and traditions also affect people's access to food security according to (Global Food and Nutrition Security, 2015). That is why, (Catalla, Rebecca Farma, 1996) that the availability of government and/or noon-governmental food program to alleviate the lack-of-food conditions among the power groups of a society in a

form of four-for-work programs, food stamps or food vouchers or public distribution programs frequently at urban based.

Supplication from Public. Being financially secured (Hawkins,B. 2018) is enough to enjoy your life in retirement is the last thing on the mind of those under the age of 30.

Adaptive to Harsh or Unpleasant Environment. In the context of (Nesting, A.) that there are two independent of comprehensive human security to achieve better environmental and social security where “environmental security” meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted to identify the factors that determine the survival strategies among non-working individuals and the framework that can be developed based on the findings.

METHODOLOGY

Exploratory factor analysis was utilized in the study. This was conducted in Davao Region with 110non-working individuals from different barangays around the city as sample respondents. A questionnaire duly presented to an examiner for content validity was the research instrument in data gathering and was personally administered by the researchers to the respondents.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was used to identify the determinants of the survival strategies of non-working individuals in Davao Region. The Keiser Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy was used to test the magnitude of partial correlations among variables. Bartlett’s test of sphericity tested whether the correlation matrix is identity matrix or not. The scree plot was used to graphically determine the number of the factors that made up survival strategy of non-working individuals in Davao Region.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section shows the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data.

KMO and Bartlett's Test. Shown below is the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity. The Kaiser Meyer Olkin measure of .805 implies that the samples are in high correlations and it allows factor analysis that fits for data. As shown, the Bartlett’s test of Sphericity yields a value of 2.447 and a level of significance smaller than .001 signifies that it allows the data to proceed factoring the survival strategy of non-working individuals. Moreover, the Bartlett’s test of Sphericity implies to reject the null hypothesis and that there are determinants for survival strategy of non-working individuals in Davao Region.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.805
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2.447E3
	Df	435
	Sig.	.000

Scree Plot. Figure 1 shows the graphical explanation of the total variance explained and the graph of the Eigen values against all the factors. The Scree Plot shows the gradual trailing of the Eigen values and identifies the relatively fit of each component based on its relative importance. The graph is very useful for determining how many factors will be retained. The point of interest is where the curve flattens. As observed, the curve gets flatter as it reach component number five since it is where Eigen value less than 1 begins. If the items of each dimension are less than minimum the dimension will be discarded. Thus, only five factors considered as determinants were retained.

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Figure 1: Graphical Explanation of Total Variance

Rotated Component Matrix. As presented in Table 1, some non-working individuals’ survival strategy attributes on the strengthening of interpersonal attachments or self-belongingness. Attributes like staying with relatives with loadings of .849 and staying with friends with loadings .795. There are non-working individuals survived through availment of outreach program. Some are using their clothes at least three days.

Table 1: Rotated Component Matrix with Group Attributes

Factors	Attributes	Loadings
1. Strengthening Interpersonal Attachment	Item15 – I stay with my relative’s house.	.849
	item16 – I stayed with my friend’s house.	.795
2. Availment of Outreach Program	Item26 – I used my clothes at least 3 times.	.662
	Item27 – I avail free clothes from outreach activities.	.619
3. Involvement on Community Celebration	Item7 – I attend wedding to avail food.	.849
	Item8 – I attend vigil to avail food.	.772
	Item9 – I prepare list of fiestas.	.713
	Item10 – I attend parties.	.658
4. Supplication from Public	Item11 – I attend government feeding programs	.559
	Item2 – I do barking in the PUJ.	.819
	Item1 – I do alms in the public.	.703
5. Adaptive to harsh or Unpleasant Environment	item4 – I offer herd cleaning.	.589
	Item18 – I sleep in public establishment (gym, purok).	.822
	Item20 – I stay in church.	712

Some non-working individual survived through their involvement on community celebration. With this, their sense of food security by way of attending wedding, fiesta and other community celebration, helped in coping up their living.

There are also non-working individuals survived because of the public. Some may ask alms in the public; do barking at PUJ and offer herd for cleaning.

Adaptive to harsh or unpleasant environment reveals to be one of the factors of the survival strategies of non-working individuals. Some spend their nights at the public establishments while others are at the church.

STUDY FRAMEWORK

Presented in Figure 2 is the framework developed based on the findings. The researchers found out that the factors of survival strategies of non-working individuals attributes in strengthening interpersonal attachments, availment of outreach program, involvement in community celebration, supplication from public and adaptive to harsh or unpleasant environment. This implies that majority of the non-working individuals survived depends on the versatility and ability to adapt fast changing society.

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that there are five factors of survival strategies on non-working individuals, namely; strengthen interpersonal attachment, availment of outreach program, involvement of community celebration, supplication from public and adaptive to harsh or unpleasant environment.

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